

Strategies for Enhancing Solid Waste Management Practices in Urban Secondary Schools in Developing Countries

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Abstract:

Effective solid waste management in urban secondary schools in developing countries is essential for mitigating environmental and health risks associated with improper waste disposal. This manuscript examines current practices and proposes strategies to enhance solid waste management in these educational settings. Current practices include efforts to reduce packaging materials, promote recycling and composting initiatives, utilize sorting and processing technologies, and implement anaerobic digestion for organic waste treatment. However, challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited resources, and insufficient awareness among

students and staff hinder effective waste management. This study also investigates current solid waste generation rates specific to urban secondary schools, highlighting variability influenced by factors like population density and consumption patterns. The environmental impact of poor waste management includes pollution of air, soil, and water, as well as habitat. Health concerns arise from disease transmission due to breeding grounds for vectors like mosquitoes in stagnant water and exposure to hazardous chemicals from improperly managed waste. To address these challenges, comprehensive strategies are proposed, encompassing infrastructure development, educational programs integrating waste management into the curriculum, community engagement, and policy advocacy. These strategies aim to promote sustainable practices, improve waste segregation, enhance recycling rates, and reduce the overall environmental footprint of urban secondary schools in developing countries. Implementation of these strategies is crucial for fostering a cleaner, healthier environment and empowering future generations with environmental stewardship values.

Keywords: *Recycling, Composting, Anaerobic digestion, Waste generation rates, Infrastructure challenges, Health impacts.*

Introduction

Solid waste generation is a significant global challenge affecting economies across various

developmental stages, including developed, developing, and least developed nations (Bui et al., 2022; Khan et al., 2022). Research indicates that the rise in solid waste production can be

attributed to factors such as population growth, increased economic prosperity, and improved standards of living (Kumari & Raghubanshi, 2023; Mian et al., 2017). The swift expansion of urban populations, economies, and energy usage in high schools in developing nations such as Nigeria, coupled with the inadequate performance of institutional authorities responsible for school planning, road infrastructure, solid waste management (SWM), and environmental stewardship, has resulted in widespread generation of solid waste in high schools. The major solid waste generated in some developing countries high school are paper, plastics, furniture, food, vegetables, stationery and cans (Chatira-Muchopa et al., 2019).

The lack of solid waste management in high schools can lead to a variety of detrimental effects, both immediate and long-term. Scientifically speaking, inadequate waste management practices contribute to environmental pollution. When organic waste, such as food scraps, is not properly disposed of or composted, it decomposes anaerobically in landfills, producing methane gas. Methane is a potent greenhouse gas that contributes to climate change by trapping heat in the atmosphere, thus exacerbating global warming (Lu et al., 2022). From a health perspective, the accumulation of improperly managed waste in high schools poses significant risks. Organic waste attracts pests such as rodents and insects, which can transmit diseases to students and staff. The presence of pests not only compromises hygiene but also contributes to indoor air quality issues and may exacerbate respiratory conditions among occupants (WHO, 2021). Additionally, decomposing organic matter emits foul odors that can create a discomforting learning and working environment, potentially impacting student attendance and academic performance (Gouge et al., 2023; Sadrizadeh et al., 2022). Effective waste management programs give students practical experience in waste reduction, recycling, and resource conservation. These programs are essential for fostering a sense of responsibility towards the environment and

empowering students to become informed and proactive global citizens. Without solid waste management in high schools, educational opportunities for teaching environmental stewardship and sustainability are lost.

Improving solid waste management (SWM) in high schools across developing countries is increasingly crucial, spurred by the migration of rural populations to urban areas and the resulting population increase. This need corresponds to at least 12 out of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Castellani et al., 2022; Sharma et al., 2021), especially those dedicated to fostering sustainable cities and communities. Various methods have been employed to gather comprehensive quantitative data on the quantity, composition, and characteristics of waste streams in schools. These approaches include reviewing waste management records, conducting visual assessments of waste, interviewing waste management personnel, and extrapolating data from similar institutions (Kasavan et al., 2021; Ugwu et al., 2020). However, direct waste analyses or waste characterization studies are the most effective methods for examining the diverse types of waste generated and identifying opportunities for waste reduction, reuse, recycling, and composting in high schools (Fereja & Chemed, 2022; Smyth et al., 2010). By implementing effective waste management practices, schools not only contribute to a cleaner and healthier environment but also instill valuable habits in students that they can carry forward into their lives beyond the classroom.

At the heart of solid waste management in secondary schools lies the recognition of the significant volume of waste generated within these institutions. From paper and plastic to food waste and electronic gadgets, schools produce a diverse range of materials that require proper handling to minimize their environmental impact (Smyth et al., 2010). An effective waste management program in secondary schools typically begins with raising awareness and educating students and staff about the importance of waste reduction, reuse, and recycling. This educational component serves as the foundation for fostering a culture

of environmental responsibility within the school community. Practical strategies such as implementing recycling bins, composting organic waste, and reducing single-use plastics are essential components of a comprehensive solid waste management plan (Oliveira & da Cal Seixas, 2019). Moreover, collaboration with local waste management authorities or recycling facilities can further enhance the effectiveness of these initiatives by ensuring that collected materials are properly processed and diverted from landfills.

Beyond waste diversion, secondary schools can also explore opportunities for waste reduction through initiatives such as promoting sustainable purchasing practices and implementing policies to minimize packaging waste. By incorporating solid waste management practices into the fabric of secondary school operations, educational institutions not only fulfill their environmental obligations but also empower students to become conscientious global citizens capable of effecting positive change in their communities and beyond.

In response to these challenges, the review will also examine various innovative approaches and initiatives being implemented in urban secondary schools across Sub-Saharan Africa. These include community-based recycling programs, partnerships with local municipalities and NGOs, and the integration of waste management education into the school curriculum. Innovative technologies such as biogas digesters for organic waste and decentralized waste processing units are also being explored to mitigate the environmental impact of waste and promote resource recovery.

Current Practices in Solid Waste Management

Current practices in solid waste management involve a comprehensive approach that integrates various methods to minimize environmental impact and promote sustainability. One of the key strategies is waste reduction at the source, which includes measures such as reducing packaging materials and

encouraging the use of reusable products. Recycling and composting are also critical components, aiming to divert significant amounts of waste from landfills by reprocessing materials and organic matter into new products or soil conditioners. Municipalities and organizations increasingly implement advanced sorting and processing technologies to enhance the efficiency of recycling programs. Energy recovery from waste, through methods such as incineration with energy capture and anaerobic digestion, provides an additional pathway to manage waste while generating energy. Landfilling, though less preferred, remains a necessary component for non-recyclable and non-combustible waste, with modern landfills designed to minimize leachate and methane emissions through advanced liners and gas collection systems. Public education and regulatory frameworks support these practices by promoting responsible waste management behaviors and ensuring compliance with environmental standards. Overall, the trend in solid waste management is towards an integrated, sustainable approach that emphasizes waste reduction, resource recovery, and minimal environmental impact.

Reducing Packaging Materials

Reducing packaging materials as a method of solid waste management in high schools presents an effective and practical approach to fostering environmental responsibility and sustainability among students. High schools and Universities in Nigeria generate significant amounts of waste daily (Ugwu et al., 2020), much of which comprises packaging materials from lunches, school supplies, and various activities (Debrah et al., 2021). Schools can potentially decrease overall waste production and impart lessons on environmental responsibility by focusing efforts on minimizing packaging (Magrini et al., 2021).

One of the most impactful strategies to reduce packaging waste in high schools is to promote the use of reusable containers for lunches and snacks. Encouraging students to bring their meals in reusable lunch boxes and containers, as opposed to disposable plastic bags and wrappers, can significantly cut down on the

volume of waste produced. Schools can support this initiative by providing incentives such as eco-friendly rewards for students who consistently use reusable containers. Additionally, cafeterias can eliminate single-use plastics and Styrofoam by offering meals on reusable trays and providing metal cutlery instead of plastic utensils. However, to achieve

significant success in this direction, snacks availability should be reduced. It was reported that snacks were the most common packaged food group in an Irish secondary school (Browne et al., 2023). Reusable containers not only reduce waste but also instills a culture of reusability and mindfulness about consumption.

Figure1. Current Practices of Solid Waste Management in High Schools

Another important aspect is the reduction of packaging in school supplies. High schools can advocate for and facilitate the purchase of bulk supplies, thereby reducing the amount of packaging waste associated with individually wrapped items (Mahmoudi & Parviziomran, 2020).

For instance, instead of individual packs of pens or markers, schools can buy these supplies in bulk and distribute them as needed. This practice not only minimizes packaging waste but also can be cost-effective for the school. Encouraging the use of digital textbooks and resources over traditional printed materials can also contribute

to waste reduction, as it lessens the need for packaging associated with printed books and paper supplies.

Educational programs are crucial in embedding the principles of waste reduction into the school culture (Antón-Peset et al., 2021; Derqui et al., 2020), because Students are concerns with volumes of waste generated and waste management. Based on research conducted in South Africa, a significant number of students expressed concern about the quantities of waste generated both nationally (80.3%) and within their respective school environments (76.1%) (Van Niekerk, 2014). High schools can

incorporate lessons on environmental science and sustainability into their curricula, highlighting the impacts of excessive packaging on the environment. Although research showed that student had a high awareness with regards to waste and waste management for both their local and national environment (Van Niekerk, 2014). Workshops and campaigns led by student environmental clubs can further promote awareness and engage the student body in hands-on activities such as clean-up drives, recycling projects, and waste audits. These activities not only educate but also empower students to take ownership of their environmental impact and make conscious choices to reduce waste.

Partnerships with local businesses and organizations can also enhance the efforts to reduce packaging waste in high schools (Tencati et al., 2016). Schools can collaborate with suppliers who are committed to sustainable practices and offer products with minimal or recyclable packaging. Local environmental organizations can provide resources, support, and expertise to help schools implement effective waste reduction programs. For instance, waste management companies can assist schools in setting up comprehensive recycling systems and educate students on proper sorting and disposal methods.

Moreover, the implementation of policies and guidelines that support waste reduction is essential. High schools can develop and enforce policies that require the use of recyclable or biodegradable packaging for any school events, fundraisers, or activities (Kragseth, 2012). Clear guidelines on waste management practices, such as mandatory recycling and composting programs, can ensure that waste reduction efforts are systematic and consistent. By involving the entire school community, including staff, students, and parents, in these policies, schools can create a collective responsibility towards waste management.

Ultimately, reducing packaging materials in high schools as a method of solid waste management not only addresses immediate waste reduction goals but also serves to cultivate a generation of

environmentally conscious individuals. Students who learn and practice waste reduction in their school years are more likely to carry these habits into adulthood, contributing to broader societal efforts to combat environmental degradation. By taking a proactive approach and integrating waste reduction practices into everyday school life, high schools can make a significant impact on reducing packaging waste and promoting sustainability for the future. In all, reducing packaging materials in high schools is a viable and effective strategy for managing solid waste. It requires a combination of policy implementation, educational efforts, and community engagement.

Recycling and Composting

Recycling and composting have become essential waste management practices within schools, addressing the pressing issue of environmental sustainability. These practices provide practical solutions to minimize waste sent to landfills, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and conserve natural resources. By incorporating recycling and composting into their daily routines, schools not only manage waste more efficiently but also serve as educational platforms that promote environmentally responsible behaviors among students.

School recycling programs typically involve the collection, sorting, and processing of recyclable materials such as paper, cardboard, plastics, metals, and glass (Cimpan et al., 2015; Smyth et al., 2010). The success of these programs hinges on several critical factors, including adequate infrastructure. Effective recycling programs require proper infrastructure, such as clearly labeled recycling bins strategically placed throughout the school premises. Additionally, schools must establish partnerships with local recycling facilities to ensure proper processing of collected materials. In Nigeria, for instance, it has been reported that students at both secondary and tertiary education levels exhibit positive environmental attitudes and possess a strong awareness of environmental issues resulting from improper waste management. However, there is a noticeable gap in the

practical education of teachers, hindering their ability to effectively guide students in implementing solid waste management practices (Debrah et al., 2021). In Palestine, for instance, it has been reported that a lack of awareness and information about waste separation and storage processes represents fundamental barriers to recycling among the local population (Kattoua et al., 2019).

Some schools have adopted single-stream recycling systems, simplifying the sorting process by allowing all recyclables to be placed in a single bin. A single-stream waste separation system is often perceived as more convenient and straightforward. This perception holds true even in developed countries, where dual-stream systems can pose challenges due to insufficient knowledge of sorting techniques. For instance, research conducted at Illinois Wesleyan University revealed that both students and teachers struggled with identifying recyclable and non-recyclable waste items in classification tests (George, 2013). However, this approach necessitates comprehensive education on what can and cannot be recycled to prevent contamination.

Active participation from students, teachers, and administrative staff is vital for the success of recycling programs. Schools that integrate recycling into their daily operations and culture often see higher engagement levels (Redman, 2013). Initiatives such as "Green Teams" or environmental clubs, where students take on leadership roles in promoting and managing recycling efforts, have proven particularly effective (Cole, 2014). These initiatives empower students to take ownership of waste management practices, fostering a sense of responsibility and leadership. Continuous education is essential to maintain and enhance recycling efforts. Schools can integrate recycling education into the curriculum, covering topics such as the environmental impact of waste, the recycling process, and the importance of resource conservation. Workshops, assemblies, and interactive activities can further enhance understanding and commitment among students and staff. Regular feedback on the success and impact of the recycling program can motivate

participants by showing tangible results of their efforts.

Successful composting programs require a well-organized system for collecting and processing organic waste. This includes placing compost bins in cafeterias, kitchens, and outdoor areas. Schools may opt for on-site composting systems, such as compost bins or tumblers, or off-site composting through partnerships with local composting facilities. On-site systems provide educational opportunities for students to engage directly with the composting process, while off-site systems can handle larger volumes of waste. Composting programs offer rich educational opportunities, allowing students to learn about decomposition, soil health, and sustainable agriculture. Schools can integrate composting into science and environmental studies curricula, providing hands-on experiences that reinforce theoretical knowledge. Additionally, showcasing the benefits of composting, such as improved soil quality in school gardens, can illustrate the positive impact of their efforts.

Recycling and composting practices in high schools promote a culture of responsibility and sustainability within the school community. They encourage students to adopt environmentally friendly behaviors, which can extend to their homes and communities. These programs often involve collaboration and teamwork, enhancing social skills and community spirit among students.

Despite the numerous benefits, schools may face challenges in implementing recycling and composting programs. Common challenges include contamination of recyclables, limited funding, and insufficient infrastructure. Contamination of recyclable and compostable materials with non-recyclable items is a significant issue. Continuous education and clear labeling of bins can mitigate this problem. Schools can conduct regular audits to identify and address contamination issues, providing feedback to the school community to improve sorting practices. Adequate infrastructure is crucial for effective recycling and composting. Schools need to invest in appropriate bins,

collection systems, and maintenance. Collaboration with local waste management authorities can provide technical support and resources to enhance infrastructure. Limited funding for infrastructure and educational resources can hinder program implementation. Schools can seek grants and partnerships with local businesses, non-profits, and government agencies to support their initiatives. Community involvement and fundraising activities can also provide additional resources.

In conclusion, recycling and composting are vital practices for waste management in schools, offering environmental, educational, and social benefits. By addressing the challenges and leveraging community support, schools can effectively implement these programs and foster a culture of sustainability.

Sorting and Processing Technologies

According to a report, the main solid waste disposal system at the school in developing countries are open dumping system (Chatira-Muchopa et al., 2019). High schools can significantly improve waste management by adopting advanced sorting and processing technologies. Automated sorting systems, such as optical scanners, magnets, and air classifiers, efficiently separate recyclables from non-recyclables within the school's waste management infrastructure (Kokoulin et al., 2020; Thayer, 1997). Optical scanners, for instance, identify and sort various plastics, while magnets and eddy current separators extract metals. Alongside automated systems, manual sorting stations strategically placed around the school, staffed by trained personnel or supervised students, ensure proper waste separation at the source. Clear labeling and instructions at these stations enhance user compliance, reducing contamination and improving recyclables' quality.

Smart bins, equipped with sensors and cameras, further enhance waste sorting. These bins detect waste types and provide real-time feedback to users, encouraging proper disposal practices (Sirawattananon et al., 2021). They also collect data on waste generation patterns, aiding schools

in identifying improvement areas and tracking waste management initiatives' effectiveness.

High schools can install on-site recycling units to process plastics, paper, and organic matter. For example, in the context of solid waste management at the University of Lagos in Nigeria, a significant proportion of hazardous waste is generated by the university's health clinic and subsequently incinerated on-site (Mbama et al., 2023). These units can shred, compact, and convert waste into reusable materials or products. For example, plastic waste can be transformed into filament for 3D printers, supporting educational projects, while on-site paper recycling produces recycled paper for school use, reducing the need for new paper purchases. Additionally, waste-to-energy (WTE) technologies, though less common, present future possibilities. In developing countries, such as Ghana, concerning waste-to-energy (WTE) technologies, research has shown that incineration ranks as the most favored method, followed by anaerobic digestion and aerobic digestion, whereas landfill gas is regarded as the least favored option (Agbejule et al., 2021). These technologies convert non-recyclable waste into energy through processes like incineration, gasification, and anaerobic digestion, offering educational opportunities about alternative energy sources and the potential of waste as a resource.

Implementing sorting and processing technologies reduces landfill waste, decreases greenhouse gas emissions, and conserves natural resources. Efficient sorting ensures recyclables are uncontaminated and viable for recycling, while composting organic waste reduces methane emissions and enriches soil health. These technologies provide hands-on learning opportunities for students, teaching practical skills in waste management, engineering, and environmental science. Integrating these technologies into the curriculum enhances students' understanding of sustainability and resource conservation.

While initial investments in sorting and processing technologies can be significant, the long-term economic benefits often outweigh the

costs (Regassa et al., 2011). Schools save money on waste disposal fees by reducing landfill waste and generate valuable materials from waste, such as compost and recycled products, offsetting operational costs. Partnerships with local businesses and organizations can support waste management initiatives, providing additional resources.

However, challenges exist, including upfront costs, training requirements, and changing waste disposal behaviors. Schools can seek grants, sponsorships, and community support to overcome financial barriers. Regular training sessions, workshops, and educational materials build necessary skills and knowledge among staff and students. Involving students in managing these systems fosters ownership and responsibility. Continuous education and awareness campaigns, supported by visual aids, clear signage, and regular feedback, encourage proper sorting and disposal practices.

The integration of sorting and processing technologies extends beyond environmental and economic benefits, providing a unique educational platform that engages students in real-world applications of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) (Guerrero et al., 2013). Participating in waste management initiatives develops students' critical thinking, problem-solving, and project management skills. These practices instill environmental stewardship and social responsibility, encouraging sustainable behaviors in personal and future professional lives. Schools that successfully implement these technologies can serve as community models, demonstrating the feasibility and benefits of advanced waste management practices.

In general, sorting and processing technologies offer an effective, multifaceted approach to waste management in high schools. By investing in these technologies, schools can reduce their environmental impact, save money, and provide valuable educational experiences. Despite challenges, strategic planning, community involvement, and continuous education can address these issues. Ultimately, adopting sorting and processing technologies fosters a culture of

sustainability, preparing students to be environmentally conscious citizens and future leaders.

Anaerobic Digestion

Anaerobic digestion (AD) represents a cutting-edge approach to waste management impact (Neelancherry et al., 2023), particularly suited to schools aiming to bolster sustainability efforts and shrink their ecological. This biological process operates without oxygen, effectively breaking down organic matter to generate biogas a blend of methane and carbon dioxide and digestate, a nutrient-rich slurry. By implementing AD, schools stand to reap myriad benefits, spanning waste reduction, renewable energy production, and enriching educational opportunities (Dirks, 2021).

The integration of AD into educational settings necessitates tailored infrastructure. Schools must invest in an anaerobic digester, ranging from modest units ideal for educational purposes to larger systems capable of processing substantial organic waste volumes. Factors such as cafeteria leftovers, garden clippings, and other biodegradables dictate the digester's size and design. Operational procedures involve gathering organic waste, feeding it into the digester, and overseeing biogas and digestate outputs. AD complements existing recycling and composting practices by handling high-moisture waste like food scraps more effectively than traditional methods, thus optimizing waste management efficiency.

Initiating an AD initiative entails considerable groundwork (Hinds, 2015). Pilot programs serve as crucial testing grounds, enabling schools to gauge feasibility, refine processes, and address challenges on a manageable scale before scaling up. These initiatives typically involve installing a compact digester, monitoring input volumes, and analyzing gas and slurry yields. Such preliminary efforts furnish invaluable insights and practical experience, smoothing the path for broader implementation.

Collaboration proves pivotal in successful AD deployment. Schools benefit from forging alliances with local authorities, waste

management entities, and academic institutions, harnessing their expertise, financial backing, and access to larger-scale digestion facilities. Engaging in community-driven AD projects fosters resource sharing and mutual benefits among local stakeholders, bolstering the initiative's sustainability and educational value (Franco & Tracey, 2019; Wanjue, 2023).

The advantages of AD in schools extend beyond waste management. By diverting organic matter from landfills, AD mitigates methane emissions—a potent greenhouse gas—thus shrinking the school's carbon footprint significantly. The biogas produced serves as a renewable energy source, supplanting fossil fuels in heating, electricity generation, and possibly transportation (Seglah et al., 2023). This advancement aligns with the school's sustainability targets, curbing reliance on non-renewable energy sources. Furthermore, the digestate residue from AD functions as a nutrient-rich fertilizer, nurturing school gardens and landscapes (Jones, 2019). This closed-loop system not only minimizes waste but also replenishes soil fertility, diminishing the need for synthetic fertilizers. By exemplifying nutrient cycling, AD underpins sustainable agricultural practices, providing students with hands-on lessons in environmental stewardship.

In essence, anaerobic digestion emerges as a multifaceted solution for schools seeking holistic

waste management strategies. Beyond its technical merits, AD cultivates a culture of environmental responsibility and innovation among students, equipping them with practical skills and insights essential for navigating future sustainability challenges. As schools increasingly adopt AD, they not only enhance operational efficiency but also foster a greener, more resilient educational environment.

Current Solid Waste Generation Rates

As the world grapples with the pressing issue of environmental sustainability, the management of solid waste has emerged as a critical concern, particularly within the education sector. High schools, as vibrant hubs of learning and development, play a significant role in shaping the attitudes and behaviors of future generations towards waste management. In the context of the African continent, where rapid urbanization has led to a marked increase in the generation of solid waste, particularly in high school settings, the need for comprehensive and sustainable waste management strategies has never been more pressing (Abdulfatah, 2023; Ishaq et al., 2022). Across the diverse landscape of Africa, the generation of solid waste within high schools has become a complex and multifaceted challenge.

Figure 1. Status of Municipal Solid Waste Generation Sources in Nigeria

City	Domestic	Industrial	Commercial	Institutional	Hospital	Agricultural
Umuahia	8	12	80	-	-	-
Ibadan	66.1	11.4	208	-	-	-
Zaria	49	14	23	10	4	-
Abeokuta	73.9	0.5	17.5	-	-	8.2
Akure	70.3	4.8	18.6	-	-	63
Ado-Ekiti	78.9	2.7	14.3	-	-	4.1
Osogbo	68.2	6.2	23.5	-	-	2.1

Note: Nnaji, 2015

The current literature highlights the significant contribution of schools to the overall solid waste generation in both developed and developing countries. According to estimates, the total generation of municipal solid waste is expected

to reach around 2.59 billion tons per annum globally by 2030 (Maalouf et al., 2020), with a strong linkage to production and consumption patterns within our societies (Halder & Singh, 2018). According to findings from a report on

solid waste generation across Nigerian states, the rates varied from 0.13 kg per capita per day in Ogbomosho to 0.71 kg per capita per day in Ado-Ekiti. Although It is noted that households contribute the largest proportion of municipal solid waste in most Nigerian cities (Nnaji, 2015).

In the context of high schools, the per capita generation rate is typically in the range of 0.5-0.8 kg/person/day, with domestic waste being the primary source (Manaf et al., 2009).

The situation is equally alarming in rural areas, where there is a dearth of scientific waste management strategies, especially in the context of underdeveloped and developing countries (Das et al., 2019). Schools also have a crucial role in increasing students' awareness of recycling and motivating them to participate in household waste management practices (Halder & Singh, 2018). Assessing waste production in schools not only highlights the contribution of school children and staff to the total amount of waste generated in a region but also reveals any poor practices of recycling in schools by the students, which could be improved through educational activities

Detailing the quantity and types of solid waste typically generated by secondary schools in Africa would provide a baseline understanding of the scale of the waste management challenge.

Addressing solid waste generation rates in high schools across Africa requires coordinated efforts from governments, educational institutions, communities, and the private sector. By implementing policies that promote waste reduction, investing in recycling infrastructure, educating students about environmental stewardship, and fostering community engagement, stakeholders can work together to mitigate the environmental, health, and social impacts of solid waste. By taking proactive measures now, African countries can create cleaner, healthier, and more sustainable school environments for current and future generations

Challenges of Secondary Schools Solid Waste Management

Solid waste management in secondary schools across developing countries, including but not limited to Africa, is fraught with numerous challenges that stem from inadequate infrastructure, financial constraints, educational gaps, regulatory issues, and cultural factors. These challenges collectively undermine efforts to implement effective waste management practices, leading to environmental degradation and health hazards within school communities.

One of the most significant issues that secondary schools in underdeveloped nations face is a lack of solid waste management facilities. Many schools lack effective waste segregation facilities, recycling infrastructure, and sufficient storage areas for various types of garbage. For example, studies in several developing nations have emphasized the lack of basic waste management infrastructure in schools, resulting in improper disposal methods such as burning or indiscriminate dumping (Muhwezi et al., 2019; Simatele & Binns, 2008). This not only contributes to environmental pollution but also poses health risks to students, staff, and nearby communities.

Financial constraints represent another significant barrier to effective waste management in secondary schools. Limited budgets often prevent schools from investing in essential waste management infrastructure, equipment, and personnel training. For example, in Kenya, secondary schools face financial challenges in acquiring waste management resources and implementing sustainable waste management practices due to competing budgetary priorities (Otieno et al., 2017). The cost of waste management infrastructure and operational expenses further strains school finances, hindering their ability to adopt environmentally friendly waste disposal methods and recycling initiatives.

Educational deficiencies among students, teachers, and administrators regarding waste management principles and practices exacerbate the problem. Many individuals in school communities lack awareness of the

environmental and health impacts of improper waste disposal. Without adequate education and training on waste segregation, recycling, and composting, schools struggle to instill sustainable behaviors among students and staff (Ike et al., 2018). This perpetuates a cycle of poor waste management practices and undermines efforts to promote environmental stewardship within school environments.

Regulatory compliance is also a challenge faced by secondary schools in developing countries. While environmental regulations exist, enforcement and adherence can be weak due to institutional weaknesses, limited resources, and inadequate monitoring mechanisms. For example, in Nigeria, secondary schools often struggle to comply with waste management regulations due to ineffective enforcement and oversight (Ezeah & Roberts, 2012). Non-compliance with regulations can lead to environmental degradation, legal repercussions, and negative public perception, highlighting the need for strengthened regulatory frameworks and enforcement measures.

Cultural and social factors significantly influence solid waste management practices in secondary schools across developing countries. Cultural attitudes towards waste disposal and environmental stewardship vary widely, impacting community engagement and participation in waste management initiatives. In some contexts, there may be a lack of emphasis on environmental sustainability or a preference for convenience over sustainable practices (Ifegbesan, 2010; Owojori et al., 2022). Addressing these cultural barriers requires tailored educational campaigns, community outreach programs, and collaboration with local stakeholders to promote a collective commitment to sustainable waste management practices.

The environmental impact of inadequate solid waste management practices in secondary schools is profound. Improper disposal methods such as open burning, landfilling, and dumping contribute to air pollution, soil contamination, and the spread of diseases. Schools located in densely populated urban areas often lack

sufficient space for waste disposal, exacerbating environmental degradation and health risks for students, staff, and neighboring communities (Mateu-Sbert et al., 2013). In conclusion, addressing the challenges of solid waste management in secondary schools in developing countries requires a holistic approach that integrates infrastructure development, financial investment, education, regulatory compliance, and community engagement. By prioritizing sustainable waste management practices, schools can mitigate environmental risks, promote resource conservation, and foster a culture of environmental stewardship among students and staff. Collaborative partnerships between government agencies, educational institutions, NGOs, and local communities are essential in advancing effective waste management solutions in secondary schools across developing countries.

Environmental Impact and Health Concerns

Poor solid waste management practices in secondary schools can lead to significant environmental and health consequences. When solid waste is improperly disposed of or neglected, it can accumulate on school grounds, creating unsanitary conditions that attract pests and vermin. This waste can include organic materials that decompose and produce foul odors, as well as stagnant water that becomes breeding grounds for disease-carrying mosquitoes and other insects (Abdel-Shafy & Mansour, 2018; Cooperband, 2000). These conditions increase the risk of vector-borne diseases such as malaria and dengue fever among students, teachers, and staff. Moreover, the presence of improperly managed waste can contaminate soil and groundwater with hazardous chemicals and pathogens, posing long-term risks to both environmental quality and human health (Olano et al., 2015).

In terms of environmental impact, poor waste management in schools contributes to pollution of air, soil, and water. Burning of waste, a common practice in some areas with inadequate disposal facilities, releases harmful pollutants

such as particulate matter, carbon monoxide, and dioxins into the air, leading to respiratory problems and other health issues for those exposed (Ana et al., 2009). The leaching of chemicals from improperly disposed waste into soil and groundwater can affect local ecosystems and biodiversity, disrupting natural habitats and potentially entering the food chain. Plastic waste, which is often not recycled or disposed of properly, poses a particularly severe threat to marine environments when it reaches rivers and oceans, contributing to marine pollution and endangering aquatic life (Obuzor & Onyedikachi, 2023; Rathod et al., 2025).

Addressing these challenges requires a multifaceted approach that includes improving waste segregation and recycling practices within schools, providing adequate waste collection and disposal infrastructure, and promoting environmental education and awareness among students and staff. Schools can implement waste segregation systems with clearly marked bins for different types of waste (e.g., recyclables, organic waste, non-recyclables) to encourage proper disposal practices (Cheng et al., 2022; Tripathi et al., 2024). Recycling initiatives can be promoted to reduce the amount of waste sent to landfills and incinerators, thereby lowering greenhouse gas emissions and conserving natural resource (Menikpura et al., 2013).

Educational programs focused on waste reduction, recycling, and environmental stewardship can empower students to adopt sustainable behaviors both within and beyond the school environment. Engaging students in hands-on activities such as composting organic waste for use in school gardens not only reduces waste but also teaches valuable lessons about resource conservation and soil health. Furthermore, partnerships with local governments, NGOs, and community organizations can provide support and resources for implementing effective waste management strategies, including waste collection drives and community clean-up efforts.

Successful examples of sustainable waste management practices in educational settings can serve as models for other schools and

communities. Programs like the Green Schools Initiative in various regions have demonstrated the positive impact of integrating environmental education with practical waste management solutions. By investing in infrastructure improvements, fostering partnerships, and promoting environmental awareness, secondary schools can contribute to a cleaner, healthier environment for current and future generations.

Recommendations

To address these challenges of lack or ineffective of waste management in high schools, the school should invest in robust waste management infrastructure, implementation of comprehensive waste reduction and recycling campaigns, integration of waste management education into school curricula, fostering partnerships with local communities and stakeholders, and advocating for supportive policies at governmental levels. By adopting these recommendations, urban secondary schools in developing countries can enhance environmental sustainability, mitigate health risks, and instill environmental stewardship among students, thereby fostering cleaner and healthier school environments for future generations.

Conclusion

Improving solid waste management in urban secondary schools in developing countries involves implementing practices like reducing packaging, recycling, composting, and using sorting technologies such as anaerobic digestion to reduce waste and raise sustainability awareness. Challenges like inadequate infrastructure, limited funding, and low stakeholder awareness require collaborative efforts among schools, governments, and communities. The significant waste generation rates, comprising organic matter, plastics, and paper, highlight the need for efficient waste collection and disposal systems tailored to educational settings. Poor waste management contributes to environmental pollution and health risks, necessitating educational

campaigns, partnerships with local recyclers, and integration of waste management into school curricula. These strategies aim to mitigate environmental harm, improve public health, and instill lifelong sustainable practices among students and staff, fostering responsible waste management in future generations.

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